

NEWSLETTER

WHAT IS GRIDFORLOADS?

The GridForLoads project (Grid Forming Loads to provide maximum flexibility and enable future power systems with very high renewable generation penetration) aims to revolutionize the stability and flexibility of future power systems. Instead of relying solely on traditional generation units for stability, GridForLoads introduces grid-forming loads, i.e. loads that can actively contribute to frequency and voltage support.

This innovation will enable the seamless integration of renewable energy sources, such as wind and solar, while reducing curtailment and maximizing renewable generation efficiency.

OBJECTIVES

- Define and validate the concept of grid-forming loads.
- Identify and demonstrate applications in electric vehicle charging, pump drives, and railway power systems.
- Develop and implement control strategies for these loads to provide grid services.
- Perform techno-economic and environmental studies to assess large-scale impact.
- Demonstrate real-world feasibility of the concept through laboratory experiments.

IMPACT

The project supports Europe's transition to a carbon-neutral power system by enhancing grid flexibility, reducing renewable energy curtailment, and minimizing dependence on fossil-based balancing units.

GridForLoads contributes to the creation of new opportunities for smart grid technologies, industrial innovation, and advanced research in power electronics and control systems.

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Project Partners:

- **5 Countries:** Spain, France, Austria, Greece and Switzerland.
- **7 Partners:**
 - **3 Research Institutions.**
 - **4 Companies.**

Events

Kick-off Meeting: Barcelona 21/01/2025- 22/01/2025

The GridForLoads Project held its KICK-OFF meeting at the CITCEA-UPC facilities in Barcelona, where partners from across Europe gathered to initiate project activities and align on technical and strategic objectives.

During the meeting, the consortium presented an overview of the project's vision, structure, and initial work plan, with a special focus on defining the concept of grid-forming loads and identifying potential application areas, such as electric vehicle chargers, pump drives, and railway systems.

PowerTech Conference: Kiel 29th June 2025

GridForLoads organized a special session titled “*Grid-Forming Loads: Can the Loads Be in Charge of Forming the Grid in Modern Power Systems?*” during the IEEE PowerTech 2025 Conference in Kiel.

The session brought together leading experts from academia and industry to discuss the innovative concept of grid-forming loads, examining its technical, economic, and regulatory dimensions. Participants exchanged insights on how loads can actively support grid stability and flexibility in future power systems with high shares of renewable energy.